

D7.1 DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION PLAN

Project: Monitoring of Environmental Practices for Sustainable Agriculture

Supported by Earth Observation

Acronym: ENVISION

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Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the dissemination and communication strategy of the ENVISION project. The main objective of the project is to fulfil the need for continuous and systematic monitoring of agricultural land, and hence shift the focus from fragmented monitoring limited to specific fields and dates to territory-wide and all-year-round monitoring.

To guarantee the success of the project, a strong communication and dissemination strategy is vital throughout the entire lifetime of the project.

This is the basis of a widespread dissemination of the overall work and results of the project, during implementation, but also beyond the project's end. This plan will serve as a guide for the project partners and at the same time will provide common tools that require the active participation of all partners.

Based on the objectives of the strategy, the defined dissemination activities are aimed at enhancing public awareness and ensure the involvement of targeted stakeholders in order to raise awareness on the objectives, activities and outcomes of the project.

The partners will use a variety of dissemination tools/activities to reach all audiences. These include among others a website, published articles and presentation of the project to conferences outcomes and objectives, events and workshops as presented in detail in this document.

1 Introduction

1.1 Project overview

Acronym:	ENVISION
Project title:	Monitoring of Environmental Practices for Sustainable Agriculture Supported by Earth Observation
Call (part) identifier	H2020-SC5-2019-2
Topic:	SC5-16-2019 Development of commercial activities and services through the use of GEOSS and Copernicus data
Duration:	1.9.2020-30.8.2023 (36 months)
Total budget:	2.735.856,25 €
Partnership:	

Table 1: Project Partners

No	Name	Short name	Country
1	DRAXIS ENVIRONMENTAL S.A.	DRXS	Greece
2	NATIONAL OBSERVATORY OF ATHENS	NOA	Greece
3	NATIONAL PAYING AGENCY	NPA	Lithuania
4	VLAAMSE GEWEST	LV	Belgium
5	ORGANISMOS AGROTIKON PLIROMON	CAPO	Cyprus
6	DOO ORGANIC CONTROL SYSTEM SUBOTICA	OCS	Serbia
7	EIGEN VERMOGEN VAN HET INSTITUT VOOR LANDBOUW – EN VISSERIJONDERZOEK	EV ILVO	Belgium
8	LINKING ENVIRONMENT AND FARMING LBG	LEAF	United Kingdom
9	THE UNIVERSITY OF READING	URDG	United Kingdom
10	ITC – INOVACIJSKO TEHNOLOŠKI GROZD MURSKA SOBOTA	ITC	Slovenia
11	ETAM ANONYMH ETAIREIA SYMBOLEYTIKON KAI MELEHTIKON YPIRESION	ETAM	Greece
12	INOSSENS DOO NOVI SAD	INOS	Serbia
13	AGRO APPS I.K.E.	Agro Apps	Greece

ENVISION aims to fulfil the need for continuous and systematic monitoring of agricultural land, shifting the focus from fragmented monitoring limited to specific fields and dates to territory-wide and all-year-round monitoring. It will make use of heterogeneous types of available data (EO-based, in situ, open data, and historical on-field check data) and state-of-the-art technologies and methodologies (automatic pixel/texture/object-oriented change detection and classification methods, machine learning, data fusion, multi-source and multi-temporal data management) for providing a fully-automated and scalable toolbox of services, built in close interaction with its future customers.

ENVISION will fully exploit the wealth of data made available through GEOSS and Copernicus and its synergetic use with other data to develop data products such as: Cultivated crop type maps; Soil Organic Carbon; Vegetation status; Crop growth (distinction of organic – conventional farming); Grassland mowing/ploughing; Soil erosion.

The ENVISION toolbox will be comprised of a monitoring service of sustainable agricultural practices, tools that Paying Agencies (Pas) & Certification Bodies (CBs) can provide to farmers for adhering to environmentally friendly agricultural practices, an Add-on Development Tool.

The project will be tested and validated in a pre-operational environment by potential future customers of its products and services. ENVISION will have three categories of business cases (Monitoring of: a) multiple environmental and climate requirements of CAP, b) soil condition, and c) organic farming requirements) and will also be tested by a group of Lighthouse Customers.

A market analysis, business model experimentation techniques and appropriate decision-making tools will determine the commercially viable business models for the services and products of ENVISION, and define alternative business models, understand their implications and identify those that will create the greatest value.

1.2 Dissemination and Communication deliverables

Table 2: Summary of deliverables

Deliverable number	Deliverable Title	WP number	Lead beneficiary	Due date in months
D7.1	Dissemination and Communication plan	WP7	ITC	4
D7.2	Intermediate report on dissemination activities	WP7	ITC	18
D7.3	Draft report on dissemination activities	WP7	ITC	34
D7.4	Final report on dissemination activities	WP7	ITC	36

1.3 Dissemination and Communication organization

The Communication Strategy is designed to help the project partners communicate effectively **to achieve the project's core objectives**. It provides a **useful roadmap for identifying who needs to be reached** and **what and when they need to hear** to ensure the project is a success.

'Communications' must be understood as a strategic project tool, which contributes to achieving the project's objectives.

Each partner organization appoints a communication manager responsible for implementing the communication plan at the partner organization level. The Lead Partner is appointed by the Project Communication Manager, who coordinates the project level's communication activities.

In the case of the ENVISION project, this person is Aleksandra Kocet (ITC Murska Sobota). Together with the communication managers at individual partners, they form a project communication group ENVISION:

Table 3: List of communication managers at individual partners

Partner	Name and surname	e-mail	Phone Number
DRXS	Panagiota Syropoulou	syropoulou.p@draxis.gr	+30 2310 274566
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AgroApps	Ifigeneia Tsioutsia	iftsioutsia@agroapps.gr	+30 2310253610

2 Communication strategy and target audience

The implementation of the dissemination and communication activities of ENVISION will be tailored around key target groups. ENVISION adopts a multi-sectoral and multi-stakeholder approach, focusing on key players and stakeholders all along the process of monitoring environmentally friendly agricultural practices, including public authorities, economic actors and citizens. The main target audiences, along with key messages, have been identified and will be the focal point of the Dissemination and Communication strategy.

2.1 ENVISION communication strategy

ENVISION overall communication strategy and concept is depicted in the figure below:

Figure 1: Envision communication strategy

Additional explanatory descriptions of the ENVISION project, to be conveyed to the target groups and stakeholders is depicted in the table below:

Table 4:ENVISION project descriptions

Description
<p>ENVISION contributes in the achievement of CAP’s environmental objectives, offering the tools for the continuous, large scale and uninterrupted monitoring of farm management activities with regards to sustainability. These tools reinforce the monitoring of environmental- and climate-friendly agricultural practices stemming from EU policy ensuring that the agricultural activities do not severely impact the climate and nature.</p>
Data and Data Products
<p>ENVISION fully exploits the wealth of data made available through GEOSS and Copernicus and its synergetic use with other data to develop data products such as: Cultivated crop type maps; Soil Organic Carbon; Distinction of organic – conventional farming; Grassland mowing/ploughing; Soil erosion.</p> <p>It makes use of heterogeneous types of available data (EO-based, in situ, open data, and historical on-field check data) and state-of-the-art technologies and methodologies (automatic pixel/texture/object-oriented change detection and classification methods, machine learning, data fusion, multi-source and multi-temporal data management) for providing a fully-automated and scalable toolbox of services, built in close interaction with its future customers.</p>
Services
<p>The toolbox of services addresses existing gaps in compliance and monitoring processes of agri-environmental and climate rules for CAP post-2020 era while facilitating farmers towards more sustainable agricultural practices. Therefore, the ENVISION toolbox is a concrete set of tools that PAs & CBs can provide to farmers for adhering to environmentally friendly agricultural practices, as well as an Add-on Development Tool that can be used by third-party developers to extent ENVISION functionality. The ENVISION monitoring service identifies unsustainable agriculture practices that can result to the following interrelated environmental impacts: Soil degradation; Biodiversity loss; Landscape degradation; GHG emissions; Water pollution.</p>
Business Cases
<p>ENVISION develops services that best fit the needs of PAs and OCBs helping them to master the complex processes of monitoring farmers’ performance in relation to the environmental rules stemming from EU policy. These services will be tested and validated in an operational environment not only by the project pilot partners but also by a group of Lighthouse Customers. A market analysis, business model experimentation techniques and appropriate decision-making tools will determine the commercially viable business models for the services and products of ENVISION, and define alternative business models, understand their implications and identify those that will create the greatest value.</p>

2.2 ENVISION key target audience

The key target audience represents the backbone of the communication and dissemination strategy and is depicted in figure below, while being explained in detail, together with their corresponding key messages.

Direct target groups (PAs & CBs):

- Paying Agencies
- Certification Bodies

Industry and private companies:

- Industry
- ICT companies
- SMEs and Startups
- Solution providers

Producers and Producer organizations

- Farmers
- Farmer associations
- Agricultural cooperatives
- Chamber of Agriculture

Researchers and Academia

- Knowledge institutions
- Research organizations
- Competence centers

The public and other interested parties:

- The public
- Service providers (banks, insurance companies, ...)
- National/Regional/Local government, e.g., Public authorities, municipalities and civil protection agencies
- Digital Innovation Hubs
- Environmental organizations (National/World-wide) & NGOs
- National/Regional/local press
- EU Bodies, networks and projects
- Media

Figure 2: ENVISION key target audience

Direct target groups (PAs & CBs)

PAs and CBs are the driving force and the primary potential customers of the ENVISION services. They are unleashing the business potential in each country and encompass other target groups, such as farmers, cooperatives, governments and other.

Paying Agencies are responsible for monitoring farmers' performance in relation to the environmental rules stemming from EU policy to ensure that farmers rightfully receive subsidies for their good practices.

Regarding agricultural certifications within Europe, inspection and certification for agricultural products are conducted by Certification Bodies.

Interest in ENVISION

- Access to high-quality services, directly raising efficiency of their work and increasing environmental protection, through use of new technologies;
- Reduction of on-farm inspections and administrative burden.

Key messages:

- ✓ PAs and CBs are at the heart of ENVISION project and are acting as primary target groups
- ✓ ENVISION is providing key technologies and tools which allows PAs and CBs increasing efficiency at their work, and trust among actors, reduce costs (inspections) and reduce administrative burdens
- ✓ ENVISION is helping PAs and CBs in becoming evangelists of sustainable and environmentally friendly farming practices
- ✓ ENVISION is providing commercial services to PAs that have the intention to use the technology for their checks

Industry and private companies

Industry and private companies (from the agri-food sector and ICT sector) as well as companies that draw economic activity around agriculture (applications, equipment, etc.) and environmental technologies are important actors at the phase of utilizing ENVISION outputs. Target groups such as large industry actors (agriculture, ICT), SMEs, Startups, mid-caps are interested in utilizing open based ENVISION platform and toolbox and providing new specific apps and services for other target groups.

Interest in ENVISION

- Development of added-value commercial services for farmers and other target groups;
- Exploitation of project's open source results;
- Inspiration for new ideas and applications.

Key messages:

- ✓ ENVISION will help develop ideas, support industry and private companies in innovating, replicating and scaling-up applications and services
- ✓ ENVISION consortium will be open for close cooperation with industry and private companies, supporting them in their technology innovation process

- ✓ ENVISION will be sharing leading edge technologies, knowledge, applications and services with all those industry and private companies

Producers and Producer organizations

ENVISION will play an essential role in changing farming practices in many positive ways. Conveying these messages to farmers, farmer associations, agricultural cooperatives and Chamber of commerce representatives (especially public advisory service) is utmost important.

Interest in ENVISION

- Support farmers in complying with regulations and using ENVISION to provide information to their paying agency or their consultants;
- Increased transparency in monitoring of environmentally friendly agricultural practices.

Key messages:

- ✓ ENVISIONs is providing very important tools and services for digital transformation of farmers and their farming practices
- ✓ ENVISION outputs, tools and services shall be presented and demonstrated to the farming community in order to increase awareness and acceptance of advanced technologies, methodologies and practices
- ✓ ENVISION is placing farmers and farming community at the forefront and value their opinion, feedback and participation
- ✓ Farmers are the main users of agricultural innovations; therefore their contributions are vital for the transformation of European farming sector into a high-tech, environmentally-friendly and sustainable industry

Researchers and Academia

Researchers and Academia are represented by Individuals engaged in research initiatives/projects and/or working in research/academic institutes or conducting core or application research on Earth Observation and environmental monitoring. They mostly constitute the perfect environment around which new knowledge is being developed, being the forerunner of change. They are very important target group for attract those target groups that seek leading edge knowledge and technologies. They are represented by:

- Knowledge institutions
- Research organizations
- Competence centres

Interest in ENVISION

- Access to research results on the use of EO for monitoring of environmentally-friendly agricultural practices;
- Further advancements on the EO/environmental monitoring research through extension/reuse of the project`s outputs;
- Inspiration for future research initiatives based on the project`s concept and results;
- Mutual learning and exchange of experience.

Key messages:

- ✓ ENVISION will provide innovative platform, services and apps that will require research and leading-edge knowledge as input
- ✓ Scientific and technical publications from ENVISION are providing very important contribution to the academic society and serve as evidence of collaboration with Research and Academia
- ✓ ENVISION technical outputs are open and reusable for further research activities to be conducted by Research and Academia
- ✓ Through Research and Academia, all other target groups will get access to the latest knowledge and information on digital technologies
- ✓ Create network of research institutions to engage the greater scientific community

The public and other interested parties

Following public and other interested parties are relevant and targeted in the ENVISION communication:

- The public
- Service providers (banks, insurance companies, ...)
- National/Regional/Local government
- Digital Innovation Hubs
- Environmental organizations & NGOs
- National/Regional/local press
- EU Bodies, networks and projects

Interest in ENVISION

- Explain the purpose and results of ENVISION to all parties in their own understandable language;
- See the benefits of ENVISION;
- Being able to understand how new and innovative EO technologies, platforms, applications and services can be beneficial for them.

Key messages:

- ✓ ENVISION is highly important for preserving environment to the benefit of all people
- ✓ ENVISION will clearly explain and promote technological innovation to the larger audience
- ✓ The public is more and more engaged and actively participating in shaping policies and co-deciding in matters of common interest for them
- ✓ ENVISION will promote results and technologies in accessible language, close to any person without technical background
- ✓ ENVISION will change the way how service providers and financial businesses (like banks, insurance companies, ...) are performing their operations in the future
- ✓ National/regional/local governments are motivated and are endorsing digital transformation of farming sector, especially those increasing public well-being, preserving environment and rural sustainability. Raise awareness of the fact that EO data is a cost-effective source of a wide-variety of valuable data
- ✓ The project will provide results and achievements which will contribute to evolving monitoring of land use in the future
- ✓ Accomplishments of lighthouse demonstrators take place at a national level but further enhancement, promotion and transferability across borders is promoted by ENVISION

- ✓ The EU institutions work together to boost and facilitate the uptake of innovative solutions in Europe
- ✓ ENVISION is all about adoption of novel technologies, solutions and services in agriculture in Europe
- ✓ Sustainability, open innovation and free access are the key drivers of the ENVISION project
- ✓ ENVISION promotes environmental protection, equal treatment for all farmers and ethical innovation principles

3 Dissemination and communication phases

Dissemination activities of ENVISION will be carried out in three main phases.

Table 5: Phases of dissemination strategy tools and activities

Phase	Focus/Main objectives	Key dissemination activities and tools
Phase 1: (M1-M18)	Initial phase: Approach-oriented Content: project presentation, objectives, expected results.	Printed material, website, 1st, and 2nd e-newsletters, press releases, social media, personal interaction.
Phase 2: (M19-M34)	Pre-operational phase: Create a more "targeted awareness" regarding techniques towards researchers, industry key players and stakeholders, relevant industry associations and local communities, and engage farmers who will provide data. Promotion of business cases.	Focused publications, 3rd, 4th, and 5th e-newsletters, press releases, videos, social media, personal interaction, conferences, workshops, exhibitions, trade fairs.
Phase 3: (M30-M36)	Maturity phase: Focus on the promotion of concrete results to key stakeholders and potential customers.	Focused publications of success stories, lessons learnt, standardisation activities.

3.1 Impact of COVID-19 on the dissemination and communication

The economic, social and cultural effects of this global health crisis are far-reaching. COVID-19 has dramatically reshaped our oral/face to face communication. Due to the current situation, there is a high possibility that no physical events will be held, neither between the project partners nor with external stakeholders. In the current situation, we adopt a proactive approach. Communication tools, especially online tools, have great value.

- Regular updating the ENVISION website: besides the static project information, the website will contain dynamic information that will be updated regularly through the project,
- Active on social media: One of the clear outcomes of the current situation is that social media consumption is rising. Currently, we have opened the ENVISION LinkedIn, Twitter, and Facebook. In the future, we will add YouTube and SlideShare.
- Regular newsletter: With newsletters, we will stay in touch with different stakeholders.
- Organizing virtual events: Travel bans make it difficult for all partners to have meetings in person. Essential meetings should, whenever possible, be held via videoconferencing instead of postponing them completely.

We will do our best to ensure the impact of COVID-19 on the ongoing project is minimized as much as possible.

4 Communication tools and plan

Every project needs to have a common and recognisable “communication language” that Partners can use to interact with each other and externally communicate the project. WP7 produced a communication toolbox for that purpose with the key instruments that build up the ENVISION identity. These elements are the foundation of all the following online and offline communication tools developed within ENVISION.

4.1 ENVISION website

Number	C1
Name	ENVISION website
Start date	September 2020
End date	Page established by December 2020, regular updates will be done.
Description	<p>The ENVISION website (https://envision-h2020.eu/) will be the main interface for communication with the public and will be updated regularly.</p> <p>It contains information related to the objectives and goals of ENVISION, the project partners, proposed activities, demo videos, news and events, organised workshops and achieved results.</p> <p>The website also links to the ENVISION social media pages and contains a contact form and a sign-up form for the project newsletter. The website will be updated regularly by the webmaster with input from partners.</p> <p>Website traffic will be monitored using Google Analytics which provides data on users and their interactions with the site.</p> <p>Mass media communication and press releases will be produced and made available on the project website. There will be a special focus on targeting local and European electronic media.</p>
Quantity	1 (KPI: 10.000 numbers of visits to the project website)
Responsibility	ITC
Evidence/Monitoring	https://envision-h2020.eu/ (Google Analytics)

4.2 A commercial mini-site

Number	C2
Name	A commercial mini-site
Start date	April 2022
End date	Page established by September 2022, regular updates to be done.

Description	A commercial mini-site will be developed when the service is in pre-operational mode, and the first results of its intermediate evaluation are available. It will present the commercial ENVISION service and serve as the primary online marketing tool for hosting the service brand in order to communicate with potential customers.
Quantity	1
Responsibility	ITC
Evidence/Monitoring	A commercial mini-site report (use Word_ENVISION_Template.docx)

4.3 Social Media

Number	C3
Name	Social Media (Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook, YouTube, SlideShare)
Start date	September 2020
End date	August 2023
Description	To reach a broad target audience, the use of social media is essential. A strong social media presence will help ENVISION reach a broader audience, and especially stakeholders who are difficult to reach through direct personal interaction. WP leader is responsible to keep it update, and every project partner is asked to send news and relevant information to the WP leader.
Quantity	5 (KPI: 1.200 Followers on social networks, 1.200 posts on social networks relevant to project)
Responsibility	ITC (All partners to contribute)
Evidence/Monitoring	Social Media Analytics

Table 6: Social Media Channels

Social Media Channel	Direct Link
Twitter	https://twitter.com/EnvisionH2020
LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/envision-h2020/
Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/EnvisionH2020/
YouTube	/
SlideShare	/

4.4 Animation video

Number	C4
Name	Animation video
Start date	January 2022

End date	March 2022
Description	Promo video will be produced and made available on the project website and social media, as well as presented in project events.
Quantity	1 (KPI: 600 animation video of project views in YouTube)
Responsibility	ITC, DRXS
Evidence/Monitoring	Video

4.5 ENVISION e-Newsletters

Number	C5
Name	ENVISION e-Newsletters
Start date	February 2021
End date	February 2023
Description	<p>ENVISION e-Newsletters will be released every six months, offering the project community with an overview of the latest project activities and developments. e-Newsletters will be both uploaded on the project website and distributed a list of recipients. The existing Network of Interest formed during the RECAP project will be used and expanded.</p> <p>The newsletter will be created through MailChimp, a web-based e-mail marketing service. It will be distributed to a mailing list containing subscriber information gathered through a sign-up form on the website.</p> <p>Partners may also promote the newsletter through their channels. An unsubscribe/opt-out link will be available as per EU directive 2002/58/EC. Contributions will be sought from all partners and particularly WP leaders. The first edition will be published in February 2021.</p>
Quantity	5 (KPI: 5.000 recipients of project e-Newsletters)
Responsibility	ITC editing, ALL partners contributing
Evidence/Monitoring	e-Newsletters

4.6 ENVISION promotional material

Number	C6
Name	ENVISION promotional material
Start date	September 2020
End date	December 2021
Description	The BROCHURE will be the main promotional material to be delivered to stakeholders. The brochures represent the main source of information on paper about ENVISION, hence they will be of great importance during events or presentations.

	<p>LEAFLETS will be created for supporting the dissemination and promotion activities and will be tailored to business case` specific.</p> <p>The project ROLL UP and POSTERS will be created for presentation both at ENVISION`s as well as external events.</p> <p>Roll-ups are an important visual tool for display at seminars, conferences, workshops or similar events. Roll-ups will showcase general information on the project and members. These will fit with the visual identity style and will also reflect the style of the website.</p> <p>The promotional material will be translated into local languages and customised in each case to highlight the specific benefits in the respective countries.</p>
Quantity	3000 Brochure and Leaflets 1 Roll up 1 Posters
Responsibility	ITC
Evidence/Monitoring	Brochure, leaflet, roll up, poster

4.7 EuroGEOSS showcase

Number	C7
Name	EuroGEOSS showcase
Start date	January 2021
End date	March 2021
Description	An expression of Intent will be filed to the EuroGEOSS initiative with the aim to accelerate the project`s market uptake within Europe, by forming voluntary partnerships with relevant EO stakeholders.
Quantity	1
Responsibility	DRXS
Evidence/Monitoring	Expression of interest signed by EuroGEOSS and ENVISION LP

4.8 Hackathon

Number	C8
Name	Hackathon
Start date	February 2022
End date	May 2022
Description	A hackathon will be organized by DRXS on solutions and applications that can leverage the ENVISION data and services into valuable input/tools for agricultural consultants. Potential applications will be: helping farmers to be more efficient in scheduling their every-day farm activities, in crop planning and in improving sustainability and climate resilience of their farms. Participants invited will be individuals and

	teams of a range of backgrounds and expertise including agronomists, software developers, GIS experts, data experts, scientists and anyone interested in visualizing data or providing solutions to problems via the use of data. Students, PhDs, young scientists, engineers, businesspeople, entrepreneurs, entrepreneurs-to-be as well as new technology enthusiasts will be addressed. Experts from industry and academia will explain to participants all the aspects of modern farming and will present to them successful cases/examples of best practices, how EO and climate data have been used to develop innovative solutions for the agricultural sector. A technical training will take part so that the participants will be provided with the necessary knowledge and guidance on how to access the Copernicus data and services and how to use them in their implementations.
Quantity	1
Responsibility	DRXS
Evidence/Monitoring	Event Report (Use Event_report_ENVISION_Template.docx)

4.9 Meetings with developers, open-source communities

Number	C9
Name	Meetings with developers, open-source communities
Start date	January 2021
End date	December 2022
Description	Meetings with developers and open-source communities will be organised.
Quantity	10
Responsibility	DRXS 2, NOA 4, EV ILVO 2, AgroApps 2, ALL partners
Evidence/Monitoring	Meeting report (Use SH_TG_Meeting_report_ENVISION_Template.docx)

4.10 Informal person-to-person meetings with stakeholders

Number	C10
Name	Informal person-to-person meetings with stakeholders
Start date	January 2022
End date	August 2023
Description	On-site visits to targeted potential customers and meetings with stakeholders at national and EU level will be organised. These meetings will be held beyond the project events aiming at presenting ENVISION's results and activities at different stages of the project development.
Quantity	80
Responsibility	All partners, 6 per partner
Evidence/Monitoring	Meeting Report

	(Use SH_TG_Meeting_report_ENVISION_Template.docx)
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4.11 Policy session

Number	C11
Name	Policy session (meetings with PA, CB, Farm Associations, EO companies/institutions, EU institutions)
Start date	March 2022
End date	May 2022
Description	<p>A Policy session will be organised, inviting stakeholders from organisations such as with invited officers from DG AGRI and DG GROW, DG CNCT, REA and the European Space Agency (ESA), aiming at:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Informing policy officers involved in the CAP implementation and monitoring, about the project objectives and activities; o Initiating a discussion to identify complementarities, seeking to develop synergies with initiatives and relevant policy actions by DGs and Agencies; o Receiving input on the shape of things to come in the future CAP and the potential of ENVISION to anticipate changes in the policy changes post 2020.
Quantity	1
Responsibility	TBD
Evidence/Monitoring	Meeting Report (Use SH_TG_Meeting_report_ENVISION_Template.docx)

4.12 Project events (seminars/workshops)

Number	C12
Name	Project events (seminars/workshops)
Start date	January 2022
End date	February 2023
Description	<p>Project events will be organized to present an overview of the project activities, disseminate project results, and share experiences/lessons learnt. For example, regional launching events/workshops will start the demonstration phase in participating countries and will allow local business case partners to better involve actors as well as attract the interest of other stakeholders.</p> <p>The creation of networks and fruitful relationships also encompasses face-to-face encounters, which allow a direct exchange of knowledge</p>

	and expertise. In this regard, the organisation of and participation in events represent a great opportunity to enhance ENVISION visibility.
Quantity	8
Responsibility	DRXS, NPA, CAPO, EV ILVO, LEAF, ITC, INOS, AgroApps
Evidence/Monitoring	Event Report (Use Event_report_ENVISION_Template.docx)

4.13 Clustering events/workshops

Number	C13
Name	Clustering events/workshops
Start date	March 2022
End date	March 2023
Description	Clustering events/workshops will be organised to enhance the visibility of ENVISION and explore common activities with other projects. Indicatively, two workshops for liaison and clustering with other EC projects will be organised in Brussels, aiming at bringing together relevant EC projects, policy-makers, regulators and Commission representatives. This will help to avoid repetition within projects, allow for cross-fertilization of ideas, provide policy advice, and strengthen international cooperation.
Quantity	2
Responsibility	ITC
Evidence/Monitoring	Event Report (Use Event_report_ENVISION_Template.docx)

4.14 External events

Number	C14
Name	External events
Start date	June 2021
End date	August 2023
Description	External events (industry fairs, conferences and meetings) will be attended by the project partners where they will present ENVISION, its activities and results.
Quantity	15
Responsibility	All partners: DRXS 2, INOS 2, Other partners 1
Evidence/Monitoring	Event Report (Use Event_report_ENVISION_Template.docx)

The table below provides a list of indicative relevant events.

Table 7: Indicative events for the dissemination of results

Name	Organizer	Type	Planned month / year	Partners attending (plan)
Panta Rhei conferences of the EU Paying Agencies		Events take place twice a year, in spring and autumn.	2021	NPA
EIP-AGRI workshops	EIP-AGRI	Single	2021, 2022	Partners
JRC MARS Conferences	JRC	Annual	2021, 2022	NOA
DG AGRI: Agricultural Outlook conferences	European Commission	Annual	2020	Partners
INSPIRE CONFERENCE, EU	European Commission	Annual	2021	Partners
Hellenic Association for Information and Communication Technologies in Agriculture, Food and Environment (HAICTA)	HAICTA, AUTH, CERTH, ELGO	Biannual	October 2022	NOA, AGRO, EV ILVO
EU Green Week, conferences on environment and greening strategies	European Commission	Annual	2021	Partners
Agricultural Economics Society Annual Conference	Agricultural Economics Society (AES)	Annual	March	UREAD
AGU Fall meeting 2022	American Geophysical Union	Annual	16/12/2022	NOA
EGU General Assembly	European Geoscience Union	Annual	2021	NOA
AGU Fall meeting 2022	American Geophysical Union	Annual	16/12/2022	NOA
ESA EO Phi-Week 2021	ESA/ESRIN	Annual	October 2021	NOA, AGRO, EV ILVO
EARSeL Symposium 2021	European Association of Remote Sensing Laboratories	Annual	10/6/2021	NOA

Conferences of Directors of EU Paying Agencies		Biannual		NPA
Learning Network platform, informal meetings		Throughout the year	Throughout the year	NPA
DG AGRI: Agricultural Outlook conference		Annual		NPA
Baltic-Polish conferences of EU Paying Agencies (Lithuania, Latvia, Estonia, Poland)		Annual		NPA
International agricultural exhibitions AGRO BALT, KAŲ PASĖSI in Lithuania		Biennial		NPA
National conferences on area-based measures in Lithuania		Throughout the year	Throughout the year	NPA
EO 4 Agriculture Under Pressure	ESA / EC	Annual	September 2021	NOA, AGRO, EV ILVO
4 th Conference of Geographic Information Systems and Spatial Analysis in Agriculture and the Environment	Agricultural University of Athens	Biannual	December 2021	NOA, AGRO, EV ILVO
14 th International Symposium on Environmental Software Systems (ISESS'2022)	Wageningen Data Competence Centre	Biannual	February 2022	NOA, AGRO, EV ILVO

4.15 Presentations/attending at International Conferences

Number	C15
Name	Presentation/attending at International Conferences
Start date	June 2021
End date	August 2023
Description	The partners will attend International Conferences, some of relevant conferences are included in Table 6.
Quantity	20
Responsibility	All partners: DRXS 3, NOA, NPA, ETAM, INOS, AgroApps 2, other 1
Evidence/Monitoring	Event Report (Use Event_report_ENVISION_Template.docx)

4.16 PR articles published in national/regional/European press

Number	C16
Name	PR articles published in national/regional/European press
Start date	January 2021

End date	August 2023
Description	PR articles published in national/regional/European press are important dissemination channels for sharing ENVISION results in the community.
Quantity	100
Responsibility	All partners
Evidence/Monitoring	Article

4.17 Publications in business journals

Number	C17
Name	Publications in business journals
Start date	September 2021
End date	August 2023
Description	Publications in business journals offer an effective way to disseminate high-level project information as well as attracting the interest of various target groups.
Quantity	10
Responsibility	All partners
Evidence/Monitoring	Publication (link or pdf)

Table 8: Relevant Business journals

Business journals	Partner
Finance: https://www.finance.si/	ITC
https://www.digitalmeetsculture.net/	INOS
https://planul-de-afaceri.ro/blog/	INOS
https://www.eurologport.eu/	INOS
https://www.itproportal.com/	INOS
https://www.innovatorsmag.com/about-timeline/	INOS
https://www.ictbusiness.info/	INOS
https://tech.eu/	INOS
https://www.ekapija.com/	INOS
https://www.epixeiro.gr/	INOS
https://startupitalia.eu/	INOS
Farmers Weekly: https://www.fwi.co.uk/	URDG

Farmers Guardian: https://www.fginsight.com/	URDG
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4.18 Scientific and Technical publications

Number	C18
Name	Scientific and Technical publications
Start date	September 2021
End date	August 2023
Description	<p>Scientific and Technical publications in an innovation action are secondary to the more commercially-oriented marketing activities of industrial partners. However, they represent an important means of project result dissemination. We expect that at least three scientific papers will be published, targeting academics, researchers and relevant professionals.</p> <p>As results will start to arrive, it will be necessary to give them the right outreach in all ways possible, including through scientific publications. WP7 will of course not be primarily in charge of the content, but it will make sure to provide a good dissemination through different channels.</p>
Quantity	3
Responsibility	NOA, URDG, AgroApps
Evidence/Monitoring	Publication

Table 9: Relevant scientific journals

Scientific / Technical journal	Partner
Remote Sensing of Environment	NOA
International Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geoinformation	
Agricultural Systems	
Land Use Policy	
The Journal of Agricultural Education and Extension	
Journal of Environmental Management	
Remote Sensing Magazine	NOA
ISPRS Journal of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing	NOA
MDPI Remote Sensing	NOA, AGRO, EV ILVO

Computers and Electronics in Agriculture: An international journal	URDG
Remote Sensing of Environment	NOA, AGRO, EV ILVO
Journal of Applied Remote Sensing	NOA, AGRO, EV ILVO

4.19 Podcasts

Number	C19
Name	Podcasts
Start date	January 2021
End date	August 2023
Description	Podcasts relevant to the expertise of ENVISION's project partners will be prepared and published. Project partners will prepare 2 kind of podcasts: (1) podcast prepared by project partners where internal staff participates in podcasts related to sustainable agriculture, adopting EO data and technologies to protect the environment and (2) podcast where external stakeholders and/or target groups will give testimonials about ENVISION project and its content.
Quantity	2 per Partner (26)
Responsibility	All Partners
Evidence/Monitoring	Podcast

4.20 Meetings with PA, CB, Farm Associations, EO companies/institutions, EU institutions

Number	C20
Name	Meetings with PA, CB, Farm Associations, EO companies/institutions, EU institutions
Start date	January 2021
End date	August 2023
Description	All partners will focus on building up trust and cooperation with PA, CB, Farm Associations, EO companies/institutions, EU institutions. Amongst other actions, we will arrange meetings where they will initially introduce the project. We will keep this constant relationship alive throughout the lifespan of the whole project.
Quantity	40
Responsibility	All partners
Evidence/Monitoring	Meeting report (Use SH_TG_Meeting_report_ENVISION_Template.docx)

6 Project visual identity

The visual identity package consists of Logo and Templates for Minutes and Report, Templates for deliverables, Templates for PowerPoint presentations.

6.1 Logo

Figure 3: Project logo

The logo is the symbol of the project, the image that should unite all Partners of ENVISION.

RGB:

R: 0
G: 102
B: 51

R: 0
G: 51
B: 51

6.2 Templates

Templates for PowerPoint presentations, deliverables, events and meetings reports will be designed and shared on the Dropbox to which all partners have access.

The templates ensure a consistent and uniform way of reporting and presenting the ENVISION project internally and externally.

Figure 4: PowerPoint template

Figure 5: Template Stakeholders/target group meeting report

Figure 6: Template Event report

Figure 7: Word template

8 Social media guidelines

The guideline describes all the components and proper/recommended use of the ENVISION identity. It is intended for internal and external use so that all members implement the ENVISION identity in the right way. This creates unity in the communication of all members and increases visibility.

8.1 LinkedIn

LinkedIn offers an opportunity to connect with a very specific and growing user base. Therefore, the target audience will be sector-specific such as technical groups, researchers and academia, and professional associations. As LinkedIn is more formal in nature, posts can be longer and use language more relevant to the ENVISION project. Relevant hashtags again should be used where possible. ENVISION should also be an active participant in the conversation around sustainable agriculture supported by Earth Observation by retweeting and commenting on stories in this area.

Mentioning a connection to ENVISION in your communication/posts encourages engagement with your posts and comments and well as enables increasing your reach. Mentioning ENVISION notifies your connections allows following:

- Your followers will be able to visit ENVISION profile and connect/navigate through it.
- ENVISION administration of social media channels will be notified about your posts and they will share your posts.

To mention ENVISION in a post, you shall follow these steps:

1. Write a post or article on your LinkedIn personal or company profile. You can do this by:
 - starting a new post/article

- sharing/commenting someone else's post/article

2. In the communication, type "@" and then begin typing a name ENVISION in the box (until the system doesn't offer you to choose ENVISION profile). Choose the ENVISION profile from the list and continue/finish typing your message.

The example of such communication is following (ENVISION shall be marked in BLUE if correctly written).

Use LinkedIn hashtags

Adding hashtags to your LinkedIn posts and articles gives them a higher chance of being discovered by LinkedIn members who follow or search for the hashtag you've used.

How to add hashtags to your LinkedIn update:

1. Write a post or article on your LinkedIn personal or company profile.
2. Add hashtags in front of words you would like to highlight for search criteria, using the # symbol.

RELEVANT HASHTAGS:

#EuroGEO #agriculture #earthobservation #sustainable #environmental #monitoringsystem #payingagency #codesigning #cocreation #farms #farming #agritech #innovation #certifications #certifyingbodies

8.2 Twitter

Twitter offers an ideal platform to connect with all target audiences – the wider public and the professional community. The main objective is to build a range of followers that are interested in the agri-tech space as well as the ENVISION project. This will enable communication and dissemination of the project activities. Posts should be concise due to the nature of the Twitter platform. An image should be used where possible to support the content. Similarly, hashtags # should be included to help categorise the Tweet e.g. #earthobservation. Relevant posts mentioning ENVISION or work in the agri-tech space will also be retweeted.

To mention ENVISION and adding hashtags to your Twitter posts, you shall follow the same steps that in the chapter about LinkedIn.

8.3 Facebook

Facebook targets both professional and individual users and is effective for building relationships and showing the human side of the ENVISION project i.e. the partners, the events and presentations being attended, the marketing materials produced. The content should be more relaxed than Twitter and LinkedIn and overly scientific language should be avoided. Posts should be accompanied by an image where possible as this delivers stronger engagement levels.

Tagging is when you write a Facebook status update and provide a link to someone's business page. When you tag a page ENVISION, that business is alerted that you've shared something. When people see the update, they can click ENVISION to visit the personal timeline. Facebook will alert us if ENVISION has been tagged in a status update.

10 Annexes

1. ENVISION_DC toolbox.xlsx
2. Power_point_ENVISION_Template.pptx
3. Event_report_ENVISION_Template.docx
4. SH_TG_Meeting_report_ENVISION_Template.docx
5. Word_ENVISION_Template.docx

End of Document

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